

SCHOLARS' POINTS TO TEACHING VOCABULARY IN ESP CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the thesis is to outline the various scholars' opinions regarding the significance of vocabulary instruction and acquisition in ESP classes. For the purpose of teaching vocabulary, information is provided on vocabulary selection, its types and appropriate techniques.

The acquisition of vocabulary and the possession of a certain number of words are essential in the process of learning English vocabulary, particularly in the English for Specific Purposes classes. This is because students can more easily engage in communication if they possess a large vocabulary. Therefore, developing academic vocabulary is crucial because students can use it in their area of interest [1; 14]. So, what are the students' options for using the vocabulary? According to Jordan [6;17], learning new words entails being able to recognize them in written or spoken form and be able to connect them to the appropriate object. In the case of ESP, the students pick up specific vocabulary associated with their field and use it in their reading, listening, speaking, and writing assignments. The technical, semi-technical, and academic vocabulary are considered as the main requirements from ESP students to be familiar with. Lexis also has to do with the development of linguistic patterns and the capacity to create new sentences by combining words in meaningful ways.

In accordance with Scrivener (2005), teachers must help students remember the vocabulary they have learned by modelling for them how to store, keep, retrieve, and use new vocabulary [9: 61]. For that reason, academic vocabulary is the main focus for ESP students. In this situation, Dudley-Evans and St. Johns (1998) contend that academic vocabulary should be taught with a higher priority because it is used more frequently in scientific and technical contexts and more frequently in general contexts. [2:75]

Hatch and Brown claim that special lexical items are found in almost every profession and that each branch has its own vocabulary to describe abstract concepts. [4: 56]. For teaching technical vocabulary, Kennedy and Bolitho distinguish between the following word categories:

- Technical abbreviations, symbols, and formulae are a contributing factor in the issues. Students should practice them in spoken and written exercises, and teachers' roles should include patiently explaining both their form and meaning to students.

- Sub-technical vocabulary, which includes words like "derivation," "conversion," "dense," and "isolation," but which frequently appear in technical and scientific texts despite not directly belonging to any one technical branch.
- Highly technical vocabulary, consisting of words with a specific technical field and a close thematic relationship. [7:90]

When teaching ESP vocabulary, the first task for teachers and material designers is to decide which words and specialized terms to actually teach. The principles of need and level are particularly emphasized by Gairns and Redman [3:59] along with cultural factors. The learnability and teachability requirements should be taken into account by both teachers and material designers. Teaching concrete words first and abstract words later is one of the most widely used vocabulary selection principles, according to Harmer. [5:154]

After choosing the words to be taught, teachers should choose what to cover in each naming unit. Harmer and Thornbury assert that understanding a word entails being aware of:

Meaning: Contextual meanings, relational sense (antonyms/synonyms),

Form includes spelling, pronunciation, affixes, and parts of speech.

Grammar includes past simple/participle forms, plurals, countability, ,

Collocations and the right register are used in usage. [8:78]

When introducing new words to students, the primary goal is to help them learn the proper pronunciation, meaning, and context of the word. It is possible to present the form and meaning of new lexical items using a variety of methods and techniques. The type of presentation that is most appropriate for a given topic depends on the teachers. There are some conventional techniques and methods for introducing new vocabulary, as stated by Gairns and Redman (73). [2: 73]

Visual techniques:

- Visuals, such as pictures, flashcards, drawings on blackboards, videos, wall charts, pictograms, and actual objects; these are helpful for teaching concrete words.
- Mime, facial expression, and gesture demonstrations are good for teaching action verbs.

Verbal techniques:

- Oral or written examples that serve as illustrations — this strategy is useful when the words being used are more ethereal.
- Synonyms and antonyms, which are taught to students by comparing them to words they already know.
- For intermediate learners, there are definitions and explanations. It can be challenging to define words, especially at the elementary level.
- Scales: If students are already familiar with big and small, for instance, teaching short and long could follow.
- Provide examples of the type of words you want to introduce.
- The most popular activity for explaining a word's meaning in classes has been translation.

Speculating based on the context, labeling, and matching - students pair words with other words, sentences, or images. It falls under the category of so-called discovery techniques because they draw on the learner's prior language skills while also introducing

new vocabulary. The use of discovery techniques calls for independent learners with advanced English skills.

In conclusion, after reading through a variety of academic works and scholars' opinions on the value of vocabulary and vocabulary-learning strategies, we came to the conclusion that every effort should be made to support vocabulary learning in ESP classrooms.

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